

SMART ERA

SMART ERA Website / D7.1

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Technical references

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* PU – Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project’s page)

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Table of contents

Table of contents	3
Executive Summary	4
1. Overview of the SMART ERA Website.....	5
1.1 Objectives of the SMART ERA Website	5
1.2 Graphic Design of the SMART ERA Website	6
2. Content Management	7
2.1 Landing Page.....	7
2.3 Development of the SMART ERA Website	8
3. Dissemination and monitoring	11
4. Conclusions	12

List of Tables

Table 1: Website accountability	5
Table 2: Landing page accountability	7
Table 3: Sections of the SMART ERA website	8

List of Figures

Figure 1: SMART ERA landing page	7
Figure 2: SMART ERA website – Homepage	10
Figure 3: SMART ERA website - Pilot regions.....	10

Executive Summary

The primary purpose of the report D7.1 “SMART ERA Website”, is to provide comprehensive evidence of the process followed during the development of the project website. It will be a reference for all the subjects engaged in the project and it will serve as the primary source of information regarding the development of the project activities, outcomes, and results.

ICONS will facilitate the process of cross linking with partner organizations websites and possible external platforms, as well as with the fellow projects, to enhance clustering activities.

1. Overview of the SMART ERA Website

The final project website was launched at the end of May 2024 (M5 in the project). It is accessible at the following link: <https://smartera-project.eu/>

The website is the entry point to SMART ERA, acting as the project’s primary platform to showcase the information on the ongoing activities, outcomes and stakeholder engagement initiatives addressing different target audiences: local rural communities’ ecosystem, policy makers, regulators, local government, institutional and public and financial, investors, financing bodies, SME’s, research and academia, members of EAB, NGO’s, CSO’s, multipliers and general public.

The website is a living tool that will be updated regularly as per the project’s requirements, in terms of new graphic layouts, tools and features.

ICONS is responsible for updating all pages on the website as new information or updates become available, in collaboration with the project’s partners. Particularly, the “News & Events” section will see more frequent updates and activities, serving as the central hub for communicating timely important updates and additions of the project.

The project website contains both institutional and scientific information about the project and serves as a channel for communicating and disseminating the project’s results. The project website also showcases public deliverables and other open access resources.

The website is designed for all viewers with unrestricted access.

Table 1: Website accountability

Accountability	The website is developed and managed by ICONS in collaboration with FBK and the project partners. To comply with General Data Protection Regulation – Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR), private data will remain confidential as ICONS will act as the data controller and be responsible for treating all the sensitive data provided by registered users upon online registration.
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1.1 Objectives of the SMART ERA Website

- The website is the official portal for SMART ERA.
- The website aims to keep all target audiences and stakeholders updated on the implementation of the project, offering resources, results, and insights from the project.
- The website provides practical information and links on the sectoral news and events: webinars, conferences, workshops, aligned with the project’s objectives.
- The website aims to stimulate clustering and synergies in relevance by highlighting the fellow projects of SMART ERA, through cross-linking activities with external platforms, relevant initiatives and partnerships.

- The website generates visibility to the SMART ERA project, promotes social media channels and fosters an online community.
- The website aims to effectively engage with a broad audience. To accomplish this objective, it employs a tone of voice that is both professional and friendly.
- The website directs users to explore the FundingBox features through a call to action, encouraging them to join the online community.

1.2 Graphic Design of the SMART ERA Website

The visual components of the SMART ERA website align seamlessly with the established visual identity crafted in collaboration with FBK during the brand identity development process, overseen by ICONS at the project's outset. This exercise aimed to delineate the project's personality, leading to the identification of the following key distinguishing concepts: smart, rural areas, innovation, rural communities, home. In the SMART ERA logo, small icons appear to specifically identify these key notions.

The emerging traits were then applied to the design process of the project website. The objective is to capture the attention of rural communities while also reaching a significant portion of the public, with a focus on broader target audiences including policymakers, local governments, and other stakeholders.

2. Content Management

2.1 Landing Page

Prior to the launch of the full website (May 2024), the landing page was released in February 2024 (M2 of the project) to serve as the first online presence and the point of reference for the project’s target audience.

The structure of the landing page was the following:

- A brief introduction to the SMART ERA project and its main objectives.
- Description of the six pilot regions.
- Contact information.
- Links to the project’s social media channels (LinkedIn and X).
- Link to subscribe to the project newsletter.
- Link to download the press release about the launch of SMART ERA project.

The layout of the landing page is available in the figure below.

Figure 1: SMART ERA landing page

Table 2: Landing page accountability

Accountability	ICONS produced the content for the landing page and was responsible for design. The content was approved by FBK before the official launch.
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2.3 Development of the SMART ERA Website

The project website was created to ensure a user-friendly experience, prioritizing easy navigation and accessibility for the users.

The structure of the website can be found in the following table:

Table 3: Sections of the SMART ERA website

Section	Description
Homepage	The structure of the Homepage stems from the landing page of the project. It is the first encounter with the user, and it features a visual from one of the projects' pilot regions, the title, communication pay-off followed by a short description, with call-to-action link to the Project section (e.g. Discover the project). The page contains the link to the project video as well as a call to action to join the online community “Funding Box” and link to the Latest Updates on the project.
Project	The Project page offers users an in-depth exploration of SMART ERA. To ensure a thorough understanding of the project's objectives, the page is structured into the following sub-sections: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vision: The page contains a description of the project's objectives, aimed at providing insight into technical and institutional information. • Rural Transformation Outcomes in Smart Era: The outcomes of the project are presented in this sub-section. • SMART ERA 4 Step Approach: This sub section includes a visual representation of the SMART ERA 4 Step Approach. • Consortium: The logos and the contact information of all the partners are displayed in this sub-section.
Pilot regions	This section is dedicated to the pilot regions of the project, where they are listed prominently. Before delving into the specifics of each pilot, users will encounter a section about rural area characteristics, accompanied by a call to action (CTA) on each page of the pilots. The pilot regions are: Trentino (Italy), Tramuntana/Sóller (Spain), Northern Ostrobothnia (Finland), East Herzegovina (Bosnia and Herzegovina), Šmarje-Padna (Slovenia, Italy, Croatia), Devetaki Plateau (Bulgaria). <p>A page for a single pilot region is structured to provide the users with as much detail about the activities implemented by SMART ERA. The communication payoff of the project is presented in the native language of each pilot at the beginning of a single page. The structure is the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to the pilot region and the payoff translated in each language. • Overcoming Obstacles: Key Challenges in Transitioning to the SMART ERA. • Targets. • Who will be a part of the change?

Clustering	<p>This page features:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The list of Macro Regional Strategies: In this sub-section the list of the 4 EU Macro Regional Strategies, all involved in the project, is provided along with the description of their objectives. • Fellow projects: In this sub-section the fellow projects of SMART ERA are listed, with links to their respective websites.
News	<p>This section on the website contains all the news regarding the project in inverse chronological order. The subcategories for the news section are the following: press releases, project updates, articles & interviews, newsletters, pilot regions, clustering & networking.</p>
Events	<p>Events organized and/or promoted by the project are listed in this section. The upcoming events are displayed first, and they are followed by past events.</p>
Resources	<p>This section houses all project publications available for viewing and download, organized into the following subsections:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverables: Public deliverables issued by the project are available in this sub-section. • Papers: Scientific papers and publications written by partners or relevant to SMART ERA are available for download. • Communication materials: The graphic communication materials produced by the project (brandbook, flyer, roll-up) are available for download on this sub-section.
Open Calls	<p>The structure of this page is the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilots Add Ons: This sub section serves as a comprehensive resource for potential applicants such as SMEs and tech providers, interested in participating in the Pilot Add-ons funding initiative of the project (first Open Call). • Followers micro-pilots: This sub section provides information about the second project funding opportunities, which will target follower regions by supporting FSTP projects. It contains details of the rules, funding eligibility and objectives for individual applicants and consortia. Additionally, it outlines the aim of transferring SMART ERA results to further rural territories, engaging their local communities and demonstrating impact potential through innovative solutions and methodologies. • Call to Action: to join the online community on the FundingBox web page.
Contacts	<p>The contact information of the Project Coordinator and Communication Secretariat for the project as well as the contact information of the individual Pilot Regions are available on this page.</p>
Privacy Notice	<p>This section contains the essential information about how the user’s personal data are processed and information about the cookies that are implemented and in use.</p>
Disclaimer	<p>This section provides information about the EU disclaimer. The quality of information complies with the Grant Agreement, according to which “any dissemination of results or outputs must also indicate that it reflects only the author’s view and that the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains”</p>

Figure 2: SMART ERA website – Homepage

Figure 3: SMART ERA website - Pilot regions

3. Dissemination and monitoring

ICONS is responsible for the dissemination of the SMART ERA website across social media platforms, as well as through news multipliers, thematic portals, and streamlined media outlets. Their role positions them as the primary conduit for journalists, media professionals, researchers, and the general public seeking access to comprehensive information on the project.

The SMART ERA consortium is invited to contribute to the dissemination efforts of the website through their respective social media channels and stakeholder networks. Close collaboration, referencing and cross-linking with the other social media platforms within the field plays a crucial role for fostering a broader online engagement.

The monitoring of the SMART ERA website throughout the duration of the project will be executed by ICONS. This activity plays a very important role in the overall DEC impact assessment strategy that will be explained in detail in D7.2 “Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results”, due by M6 (June 2024).

Data analytics will be collected using MATOMO. Relevant KPIs include website visits, resource downloads (e.g., press releases, deliverables), and average website session duration.

4. Conclusions

The SMART ERA website, managed by ICONS, will serve as the main communication channel of the project, showcasing the objectives and results and facilitating the interactions between the pilot regions, the stakeholders and the project.

The SMART ERA website plays a crucial role in maintaining the project’s visibility and sharing its outcomes. It will maintain a consistent communication tone and visual identity across the channels throughout the project.

ICONS will monitor the performance of the website as part of the communication, dissemination and exploitation impact reports foreseen during the project execution.